

May 17th, 2023
Aton University, Birmingham, UK

DEVELOPMENT OF BECCS BY COUPLING A CLC COMBUSTOR TO A GAS TURBINE

Dr Pietro Bartocci ○ ICB-CSIC (Spain)

PRESENTATION INDEX

- 1. INTRODUCTION TO BECCS
- 2. BIOFUELS TYPES
- 3. THE MARIE CURIE PROJECT GTCLC-NEG
- 4. OXYGEN CARRIERS PREPARATION
- 5. OXYGEN CARRIERS CHARACTERIZATION & PARTICLE MODEL RESULTS
- 6. BATCH TESTS
- 7. CONTINUOUS TESTS
- 8. 0D REACTOR MODEL
- 9. CFD MODELING
- 10. ASPEN MODELING
- 11. GUIDELINES
- 12. EXPLOITATION PLAN

Meet the Researcher

Dr. Pietro Bartocci

20 years of experience in BioEnergy

Marie Curie Individual Fellow at the Spanish Council of Research (CSIC) 2021-now

Visiting professor at the Institute for Clean and Renewable Energy in HUST, China 2012-2021

Assistant Professor on Energy From Biomass and Waste in Italy 2012-2020

Consultant on LCA in a University of Perugia spinoff 2016-2021

1. INTRODUCTION TO BECCS

CDR policy implementation

Carbon Dioxide Removal

- Fully functional CDR policy and/or high CDR targets
- Advanced CDR policy and/or CDR targets
- Above average CDR policy
- Average CDR policy
- Below average CDR policy

CDR investment opportunities

Why invest in UK CCUS?

A sector with ambitious targets and major opportunities for growth

£20bn

for the early deployment of CCUS¹

Up to
£210mn

Industrial Strategy Challenge Fund²

Up to
£115mn

in new R&D spending to develop CCUS & Carbon Removal techs in the UK³

Up to
£8bn

of potential turnover captured by the UK from global turnover of the CCUS industry in 2050⁴

Up to
£18bn

private financial capacity available from UK Infrastructure Bank for sectors including H2/CCUS⁵

UK aims to capture **20-30 MtCO₂** per year by 2030

Opportunities in an advanced and growing sector:

- **Global player:** the UK is in the top 5 countries globally for CCUS readiness⁵
- **CCUS clusters:** The government is committed to deploying two CCUS clusters by the mid-2020s and a further two by 2030 through which we aim to capture 20-30MtCO₂ per year
- **Regulatory environment:** Bespoke business models
- Could support **50,000 jobs in 2030**⁶

Sources: ¹Spring Budget (2023); ²Industrial Strategy Challenge Fund (2023); ³Net Zero Innovation Portfolio; ⁴Analysis based on Energy Innovation Needs Assessment (2019); ⁵UKIB Strategic Plan (2022); ⁶CO2RE (2023); ⁷Energy Innovation Needs Assessment (2019)

Costs per ton of CO₂ avoided

Technology	Value (\$/tCO ₂)
Combustion (eg Chemical Looping / Oxyfuel combustion)	88-228
Bioethanol sector	20-175
Pulp and paper mills	20-70
Biomass gasification	30-76

Consoli, C., *Bioenergy and carbon capture and storage*. Global CCS Institute, 2019.

Fuss, S., et al., *Negative emissions—Part 2: Costs, potentials and side effects*. Environmental Research Letters, 2018.

13(6):

p. 063002.

Board, O.S., E. National Academies of Sciences, and Medicine, *Negative emissions technologies and reliable sequestration: A research agenda*. 2019.

240 \$/tCO₂

Results* show that global economic costs and the carbon prices needed to hit the stabilization targets are substantially lower with the technology available, and BECCS acts as a true backstop technology at carbon prices around \$240 per ton of carbon dioxide.

* Fajardy, M., Morris, J., Gurgel, A., Herzog, H., Mac Dowell, N., & Paltsev, S. (2021). The economics of bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) deployment in a 1.5 C or 2 C world. *Global Environmental Change*, 68, 102262.

THE MARIE CURIE PROJECT GTCLC-NEG

WHAT IS THE CLC PROCESS?

Zeng, L., Cheng, Z., Fan, J.A. *et al.* Metal oxide redox chemistry for chemical looping processes. *Nat Rev Chem* **2**, 349–364 (2018).
<https://doi.org/10.1038>

What is CLC, what is a dual circulating fluidized bed reactor (DCFB)

KEY CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DCFB

- The bed is made of metal -> oxygen carrier;
- The oxygen carrier circulates between the air reactor and the fuel reactor, transporting oxygen;
- The bed reactor at a constant time is full of a certain amount of OC (Inventory), same for the Air Reactor
- The gas exchange between the air reactor and the fuel reactor is avoided by the presence of one or more loop seals

MANY CONFIGURATIONS...

PFIR (600 kWth) - CANMET

Plug-flow Internally-circulating reactor

ICR (5 kWth) - NTNU

Internally recirculated reactor (ICR)

5. Pilot-scale Unit - 50 kW_{th} Pressurized Unit

FLOWS

CRITICAL CONDITIONS:
 HIGH TEMPERATURE (1200°C)
 HIGH PRESSURE (20 bar)

**OXYGEN
 POLISHING STEP**

$$\text{Combustor efficiency} = \eta_c = \frac{2 \cdot x_{\text{CO}_2} + x_{\text{CO}} + x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{4 \cdot (x_{\text{CH}_4} + x_{\text{CO}_2} + x_{\text{CO}})}$$

Barriers

- high efficiency oxygen carriers are needed
- low attrition rate oxygen carriers are needed which can work in extreme conditions;
- kinetics aspects under high pressure and temperature conditions are not known;
- reactor injection system has to be adapted to biofuels; the use of the hot air produced from the air reactor in a gas turbine has to be optimized; exhausts should be filtered to retain the dust released by oxygen carrier attrition;

Combustion and Gasification group

Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)
- Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) -
Instituto de Carboquímica (ICB) Zaragoza

<http://www.icb.csic.es/>

2015

2016

2017

2018

Combustion and Gasification group

Research lines

- **Combustion /gasification** in bubbling and circulating fluidized bed reactors using fossil and renewable fuels (coal, biomass, wastes, etc.)
- **Hot gas cleaning. Sulphur compounds** (SO₂, H₂S, etc.) with calcium based sorbents
- **Modelling, simulation and optimisation of fluidized bed reactors**
- **CO₂ capture**
 - *Chemical Looping Combustion*
 - Oxyfuel combustion (fluidized bed)
- **Syngas/H₂ production with CO₂ capture**
 - *“Chemical Looping Reforming”*
 - *“Chemical Looping Gasification”*

Research on
Chemical Looping
since 2000

Combustion and Gasification group

Chemical looping research

Combustion and Gasification group

Chemical looping research

- More than 1500 h of experiment work in Chemical Looping units (about 20% of the global experience in CL)

CLC/CLR - 500 W_{th}
Natural gas / syngas

CLC/CLR - 500 W
Liquid fuels

CLC/CLR - 10 kW_{th}
Natural gas / syngas

Press CLR - 1 kW_{th}
Natural gas

CLC - 1 kW_{th}
Solid fuels

CLC - 50 kW_{th}
Solid fuels

Oxygen carrier preparation

Mechanical mixing

Spray granulation

Mixed oxides preparation – bimetallic oxygen carriers

NiO-based OCs are prepared based on impregnation and precipitation

- prepare suspension of the support ($\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ or $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) in a solution of urea;
- mix nickel nitrate solution into the suspension with eh support (having a urea/Ni molar ratio of 1.9)
- the slurry or suspension is kept mixing at 90°C for 20 hours (which is the aging period);
- the precipitate is filtered, washed with distilled water and dried at 100°C overnight;
- calcination is performed to transform the elemental nickel into its oxide. The conditions are: 950°C for 1 hour, using air;

Final samples

Ni18αAl

Ilmenite

Tierga Ore

Fe20γAl

MIXED Mn-Fe OCs

Iron-Manganese-Titanium based OCs

Oxygen carrier characterization & PARTICLE MODELS RESULTS

Total metal content determination

ICP-OES, Jobin Yvon 2000 spectrometer

Mean particle size

LS 13 320 Beckman Coulter equipment, according to ISO 13320 Standard

Skeletal density of the particles

Micromeritics Model AccuPyc II 1340 helium pycnometer

Crushing Strength

Shimpo FGN-5X

Porosity

Quantachrome Pore-Master 33

BET

Nitrogen at 77 K in a Micromeritics ASAP-2020 (Micromeritics Instruments Inc.)

Crystalline chemical species

Bruker AXS D8 Advance system, with Bragg-Brentano geometry configuration

Oxygen Carrier specifications

- High Oxygen transport capacities ($m_{\text{ox}} - m_{\text{red}})/m_{\text{ox}}$;
- Low Cost
- Small coke deposition
- Small tendency to agglomeration
- Resistance to attrition
- Oxygen vacancies

Why modeling an oxygen carrier particle?

AGGLOMERATION AND SINTERING

Sintering is a physical process due to crystallite growth, and agglomeration is the cohesion of neighboring particles.

Ni18- α Al₂O₃

NiO21- γ Al₂O₃

CSIC Patent:
WO2009/101233

Sample	Ni18- α Al ₂ O ₃
Method (number imp)	Hot incipient wet impregnation
Apparent density (g/cm ³)	2.5
BET surface area (m ² /g)	7
Porosity (%)	42.5
Mechanical Strength (N)	4.1
XRD phases	α -Al ₂ O ₃ , NiO, NiAl ₂ O ₄
Oxygen transport capacity*	0.21

*Referred to pure NiO and according to Adanez, J., Abad, A., Garcia-Labiano, F., Gayan, P., & De Diego, L. F. (2012). Progress in chemical-looping combustion and reforming technologies. Progress in energy and combustion science, 38(2), 215-282.

Physical properties and solid crystalline phases of the fresh OC. BET area of support: 15 m²/g for α -Al₂O₃. According to: Gayán, P., et al., NiO/Al₂O₃ oxygen carriers for chemical-looping combustion prepared by impregnation and deposition-precipitation methods. Fuel, 2009. 88(6): p. 1016-1023.

Property	Fresh material
Fe ₂ O ₃ (wt.%)	20*
Oxygen transport capacity, R _{OC}	0.02
Particle size (lm)	200-400
Skeletal density (kg/m ³)	3950
Crushing strength (N)	1.5
Porosity (%)	50.5
Specific surface area, BET (m ² /g)	39.1
XRD	Fe ₂ O ₃ , α-Al ₂ O ₃
*Determined by ICP-AES	

Property	Units	Ilmenite
Average particle diameter	μm	150-200
Bulk density	kg/m ³	2050
Apparent density	kg/m ³	3700
Crushing strength	N	3.85
Minimum fluidization velocity	m/s	0.025
Terminal Velocity	m/s	0.85
Fe-Ti Molar ratio	-	1-1-1
Mass ratio of available oxygen in the oxygen carrier	-	3.9
Oxygen transport capacity	-	0.05**
BET	m ² /g	0-0.11

Nima Khakpoor, Ehsan Mostafavi, Nader Mahinpey, Hector De la Hoz Siegler, Oxygen transport capacity and kinetic study of ilmenite ores for methane chemical-looping combustion, Energy, Volume 169, 2019, Pages 329-337,

Tierga ore (Spain)

	Tierga ore sample
XRD main phases	Fe_2O_3 , SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , CaO , MgO
Fe_2O_3 (wt%)	76.5
Oxygen transport capacity, ROC, (%) ^c	0.025
Crushing Strength	5.8
Skeletal density (kg/m^3)	4,216
Porosity (%)	26.3
Specific surface area, BET (m^2/g)	1.4

IRON-MANGANESE- TITANIUM BASED OXYGEN CARRIERS

Characteristic	Value
XRD main phases (%)	
$(\text{Mn}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_3$	95.2
$(\text{Mn}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_3\text{O}_4$	0.0
TiO_2	4.8
Crushing strength (N)	1.9
Oxygen transport capacity, ROC (%)	9.5
Porosity (%)	30
Skeletal Density (kg/m^3)	4939
Specific surface area, BET (m^2/g)	<1

PTGA Pressurised Thermogravimetric Analyzer
CAHN-

Pressurized TGA (Cahn TG-2151 type)

Redox thermogram example

Redox thermogram example (2)

EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN WITH THE PTGA

Qt (l/h)	m (mg)	T(°C)	Pt (atm)	%CH4	%CO2	%N2	Air	PCH4
240	30	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	70	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
200	50	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
175	50	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	500	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	450	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	425	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	1	30	19	51	100	0.3
240	50	475	5	6	19	75	100	0.3
240	50	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	15	2	19	79	100	0.3
240	50	475	1	3	19	78	100	0.03
240	50	475	5	3	19	78	100	0.15
240	50	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	15	3	19	78	100	0.45

All the 18 tests are performed using **Ni18- α Al₂O₃** as a catalyst

Effect of pressure at changing CH₄ concentration and constant partial pressure

Effect of pressure at changing CH_4 concentration and constant partial pressure

Explanation

Effect of pressure at constant CH_4 concentration and increasing partial pressure

Effect of pressure at constant CH_4 concentration and increasing partial pressure

Particle model

Gayan, P., Dueso, C., Abad, A., Adanez, J., de Diego, L. F., & Garcia-Labiano, F. (2009). NiO/Al₂O₃ oxygen carriers for chemical-looping combustion prepared by impregnation and deposition–precipitation methods. *Fuel*, 88(6), 1016-1023.

We consider a SCM (Shrinking Core Model) for a plate like particle.

$$\frac{t}{\tau} = X_r$$

Where:

- t is time (s)
- τ is the time for complete solid conversion (s)
- X_r is the solid conversion.

$$\frac{dX_r}{dt} = \frac{1}{\tau}$$

But we know also that:

$$X = k_r * P_g * t$$

In this way we can determine:

- E and A for changing temperatures
- k_r and d for changing pressures

Measurement of the time required for complete solids conversion at different Temperatures

$$X = k_r * P_g * t$$

$$X/t = k_r * P_g$$

$$(X/t)/P_g = k_r$$

Determination of E and A

- $k = A * e^{-E/RT}$

- $\ln(k) = \ln A - E/RT$

← Expressed in Kelvin

Determination of k_r and d

- $X = k_r * P_g * t$
- $X = k(T)/P_T^d * P_g * t \rightarrow k_r = k / P_T^d$

Preliminary results of values of E and A

BATCH TESTS

BATCH PLANT LAYOUT

REACTOR DIMENSIONS

(*data are in millimeters)

Gas flows calculation software

Material:	MnTi20					
Diameter/ μm:	100-300					
Weight / g:	300					
Density / $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$:	2547					
Emf:	0.55					
Bed height / cm:	11.43					
u_{mf} / $\text{cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	1.30					
u_t / $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	0.86					
Experiment:		[CO] / %	0			
Velocity / $\text{cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$:	20	[CH4] / %	30			
Surface / cm^2:	22.89	[H2] / %	0			
Temperatura / $^{\circ}\text{C}$:	1000	[CO2] / %	0			
Volumetric Flow (T) / $\text{l}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$:	1648.08	[H2O] / %	0			
Volumetric Flow (273 K) / $\text{l}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$:	353	[O2] / % :	10			
	Gas	Volumetric flow (l/h)	Channel	% Gas	Q gas / $\text{l}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	% Valv
reduction gases	CH4	100	A	15.0	53.0	53.0
	CO	250	C	0.0	0.0	0.0
	H2	151.5	D	35.0	123.7	81.7
	CO2	800	E	0.0	0.0	0.0
	N2	658	F	65.0	229.7	34.9
	Total					406.5
inert	N2	658	F	100.0	353.4	53.7
Oxidation gases	N2	500	G	52.4	185.1	37.0
	Aire	800	H	47.6	168.3	21.0
	Total					353
	Valve	Volumetric flow (l/h)	Channel	% Gas	Q liq / $\text{g}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	% Valv
	H2O			20.0	56.8	

TEST PROCEDURE

2 MINUTES REDUCTION

2 MINUTES INTERT GAS PURGING

ABOUT 10 MINUTES COMPLETE OXIDATION

REPEAT IN LOOP

OPEN THE REACTOR AND SAMPLE THE BED
(25g sample taken)

Sampling to check attrition

BATCH TESTS USING IRON

Experimental campaign Fe₂₀γAl

Fe₂₀Al – 950 °C

Fe₂₀Al – 1000 °C

INCOMPLETE
COMBUSTION

Fe₂₀Al – 1050 °C

Sample analysis

DENSITY

PARTICLE DIAMETER

HARDNESS

SEM

EDX

LINESCAN

TGA

ATTRITION

SOLIDS DENSITY ANALYSIS: Fe₂₀γAl

SOLIDS PARTICLE DIAMETER: Fe₂₀γAl RAW SAMPLE

Volume Statistics (Arithmetic)

Calculations from 0.375 µm to 2000 µm

Volume:	100%	S.D.:	70.42 µm
Mean:	235.4 µm	Variance:	4959 µm ²
Median:	224.5 µm	C.V.:	29.9%
Mean/Median ratio:	1.048	Skewness:	1.709 Right skewed
Mode:	223.4 µm	Kurtosis:	5.541 Leptokurtic

<10%	<25%	<50%	<75%	<90%
161.3 µm	187.3 µm	224.5 µm	269.7 µm	317.5 µm

SOLIDS PARTICLE DIAMETER: Fe₂₀γAl 1050°C SAMPLE

Volume Statistics (Arithmetic)

Calculations from 0.375 μm to 2000 μm

Volume:	100%	S.D.:	90.57 μm
Mean:	233.0 μm	Variance:	8202 μm ²
Median:	228.7 μm	C.V.:	38.9%
Mean/Median ratio:	1.019	Skewness:	0.316 Right skewed
Mode:	223.4 μm	Kurtosis:	1.840 Leptokurtic

<10%	<25%	<50%	<75%	<90%
143.7 μm	186.3 μm	228.7 μm	277.1 μm	334.5 μm

HARDNESS: Fe₂₀γAl

SOLIDS SEM ANALYSIS: Fe₂O₃/Al

RAW SAMPLE

BSECOMP 1.00mm

BSECOMP 100µm

BSECOMP 30.0µm

950°C.

BSECOMP 1.00mm

BSECOMP 200µm

BSECOMP 5.00µm

1000°C.

BSECOMP 1.00mm

BSECOMP 100µm

BSECOMP 30.0µm

1050°C

BSECOMP 1.00mm

BSECOMP 200µm

BSECOMP 30.0µm

Solids SEM analysis: Fe₂₀γAl

RAW SAMPLE

1000 °C

1050 °C

Linescan analysis: Fe₂₀yAl

RAW SAMPLE

950°C

1000°C

1050°C

EDX ANALYSIS: Fe₂₀yAl

RAW SAMPLE

950°C

Spectrum: 1

El Series	unn. [wt.%]	norm. [wt.%]	Atom. [at.%]	Error (2 Sigma) [wt.%]
C K-series	12.83	11.62	28.17	7.38
O K-series	16.13	14.61	26.58	6.43
Al K-series	13.49	12.22	13.18	1.67
Fe K-series	67.91	61.54	32.07	4.54

Total: 100.39 100.00 100.00

1000°C.

Spectrum: 1

El Series	unn. [wt.%]	norm. [wt.%]	Atom. [at.%]	Error (2 Sigma) [wt.%]
C K-series	13.95	12.92	21.62	7.91
O K-series	45.86	42.47	53.34	14.24
Al K-series	25.22	23.35	17.39	2.52
Fe K-series	22.96	21.26	7.65	1.85

Total: 110.36 100.00 100.00

1050°C

Spectrum: 1

El Series	unn. [wt.%]	norm. [wt.%]	Atom. [at.%]	Error (2 Sigma) [wt.%]
C K-series	13.95	12.92	21.62	7.91
O K-series	45.86	42.47	53.34	14.24
Al K-series	25.22	23.35	17.39	2.52
Fe K-series	22.96	21.26	7.65	1.85

Total: 107.99 100.00 100.00

TGA Analysis – Reduction: Fe₂O₃/Al

XRD: Fe₂O₃γAl

23AA275P5 (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

Raw Fe₂O₃

23AA276P3 (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

Bed 950°C

23AA277P3 (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

Bed 1000°C.

23AA278P3 (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

Bed 1050°C

The intensity depends on a number of factors, mainly the structure factor, multiplicity of plane, Lorentz factor, polarization factor, temperature and absorption factors.

Attrition: Fe₂O₃/Al

BATCH TESTS USING NICKEL

Problems in the experimental campaign with nickel (1000°C)

Nickel samples analysis with TGA

FRESH

m sample	60		
m initial N2	79.2622	m initial CH ₄	79.3645
m final N2	76.7007	m red NiO free	78.623
m final CH4	76.803		
Δm	2.5615	Δm NiO free	0.7415
NiO %	18	NiO free %	5.9
Δm theoretical	2.2680	Δm theoretical	0.7415
X	1.13	X	0.29
NiO exp	20.3%		
Δm theoretical	2.5615		

REDUCED

m sample	50.7		
m initial N2	63.5687	m initial en CH ₄	63.6697
m final N2	61.7753	m red NiO free	63.2092
m final CH4	61.8763		
Δm	1.7934	Δm NiO free	0.4605
NiO %	18	NiO free %	4.3
Δm theoretical	1.9165	Δm theoretical	0.4605
X	0.94	X	0.26
NiO exp	20.3%		
Δm theoretical	2.1613		
Xreal	0.83		

It is not reducing completely

Aluminate formation: NiAl₂O₄

Reactions of hydrocarbons in presence of NiO at high temperature

- **Main reactions**
- Combustion $C_nH_{2n+2} + (3n+1) NiO \rightarrow (3n+1) Ni + n CO_2 + (n+1) H_2O$
- Partial oxidation $C_nH_{2n+2} + n NiO \rightarrow n Ni + n CO + (n+1) H_2$
- **Reactions between gases (homogeneous reactions)**
- Steam reforming $C_nH_{2n+2} + nH_2O \rightarrow nCO + (2n+1)H_2$
- Dry reforming $C_nH_{2n+2} + nCO_2 \rightarrow 2nCO + (n+1)H_2$
- Water gas shift $CO + H_2O \rightarrow CO_2 + H_2$
- Methanation $CO + 3H_2 \rightarrow CH_4 + H_2O$
- Dehydrogenation $C_nH_{2n+2} \rightarrow C_nH_{2n} + H_2$
- Cracking $C_nH_{2n+2} \rightarrow C_{n-1}H_{2(n-1)} + CH_4$
- Carbon deposition $C_nH_{2n+2} \rightarrow n C + (n+1) H_2$
- Carbon gasification $C + H_2O \rightarrow CO + H_2$
- Boudouard $C + CO_2 \rightarrow 2CO$
- **Reaction of gases with NiO (heterogeneous reactions)**
- $CH_4 + 4NiO \rightarrow 4Ni + CO_2 + 2H_2O$
- $C_nH_{2n} + 3nNiO \rightarrow 3nNi + nCO_2 + nH_2O$
- $CO + NiO \rightarrow Ni + CO_2$
- $H_2 + NiO \rightarrow Ni + H_2O$
- $C + NiO \rightarrow CO + Ni$

Experimental campaign Ni18 α Al 950°C

Dueso, C. (2010). Combustión de gases con separación inherente de CO₂ mediante transportadores de oxígeno basados en NiO.

Experimental campaign Ni18 α Al 1000°C

Experimental campaign Ni18 α Al 1050°C

Experimental campaign Ni18 α Al 1100°C

Experimental campaign Ni18 α Al 1150°C

Experimental campaign Ni18 α Al 1200°C

Nickel attrition

CONTINUOUS TESTS

Continuous plant layout

Efficiency about 90%

Reaction mechanism (1)

Fuel Reactor (FR)

Glycerin Combustion

Glycerin Partial Oxidation

Steam Glycerin Reforming

Reaction mechanism (2)

Glycerin Decomposition

Reforming Products Oxidation

Methane Combustion

Steam Methane Reforming

Ethanol Combustion

Methanol Combustion

Methanation

Carbon Deposition

Carbon Gasification

Water-Gas Shift Reaction

Steam Oxygen-Carrier Regeneration

0D REACTOR MODEL

Validation against experimental data

➤ Dual Circulating Fluidized Bed (TUV)

A model previously developed (INNOCUOUS FP7) has been adapted to the new geometry of the CLC unit at TUV

FR	OLD	NEW
D bottom (m)	0.15	0.18
D riser (m)	0.15	0.102
Height (m)	3.10	0.75+3.05

AR	OLD	NEW
D riser (m)	0.15	0.13
Height (m)	4.10	4.03

Abad A, Adán J, García-Labiano F, de Diego LF, Gayán P. Modeling of the chemical-looping combustion of methane using a Cu-based oxygen-carrier. Combust Flame 2010;157:602–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2009.10.010>.

Abad A, Gayán P, de Diego LF, García-Labiano F, Adán J. Modelling Chemical-Looping assisted by Oxygen Uncoupling (CLaOU): Assessment of natural gas combustion with calcium manganite as oxygen carrier. Proc Combust Inst 2019;37: 4361–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2018.09.037>.

Abad A, Gayán P, García-Labiano F, de Diego LF, Adán J. Relevance of plant design on CLC process performance using a Cu-based oxygen carrier. Fuel Process Technol 2018;171:78–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2017.09.015>.

➤ Algorithm (Fortran Code ®)

- Green loop:**
 - ΔP and H_b
- Orange loop**
 - ΔX
- Pink loop**
 - FR-AR integration ($X_{in}-X_{out}$)

➤ CuO/Al₂O₃ impregnated oxygen carrier

- ✓ In general, good fitting of experimental results regarding methane conversion
- ✓ Although ΔX_{sol} is well predicted, deviation are found in $X_{O_{2,sol}}$ at the reactors inlet in some cases

Modelling pressurized-CLC

➤ Effect on fluid dynamic

$$Ar = d_p^3 \left(\frac{\rho_g(\rho_p - \rho_g)g}{\mu_g^2} \right)$$

$$Sc = \left(\frac{\mu_g}{\rho_g D} \right)$$

➤ Mass transfer in the bubbles

Modelling pressurized-CLC

➤ Effect on kinetics

energy&fuels Article
Cite This: Energy Fuels 2017, 31, 14201–14210 pubs.acs.org/EF

Reduction Kinetics of Ilmenite Ore for Pressurized Chemical Looping Combustion of Simulated Natural Gas

Yewen Tan,[✉] Firas N. Ridha, Dennis Y. Lu,[✉] and Robin W. Hughes

Natural Resources Canada, CanmetENERGY-Ottawa 1 Haanel Drive, Ottawa, Ontario K1A 1M1, Canada

$$k = 5.263 \times 10^{-25} \times P^{-0.425} \times p_{\text{Fuel}}^{0.935} \times p_{\text{CO}_2}^{-0.46} \times T^{7.36}$$

Figure 16. Individual effects on k by total pressure P , fuel partial pressure p_{Fuel} , and CO_2 partial pressure p_{CO_2} , assuming 20 vol % fuel and 20 vol % CO_2 in the reaction gas mixture.

Energy & Fuels 2006, 20, 26–33

Effect of Pressure on the Behavior of Copper-, Iron-, and Nickel-Based Oxygen Carriers for Chemical-Looping Combustion

Francisco García-Labiano,* Juan Adánez, Luis F. de Diego, Pilar Gayán, and Alberto Abad

Department of Energy and Environment, Instituto de Carboquímica (CSIC), Miguel Luesma Castán 4, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain

$$k_{0,p} = \frac{k_0}{P^i}$$

Fluidization regime in the flow map for the fuel reactor burning CH₄ with ilmenite particles.

Fig. 1. Fluidization regime in the flow map for the fuel reactor burning CH₄ with ilmenite particles. Continuous lines/symbols: reactor inlet conditions. Dashed lines/symbols: reactor outlet conditions. Selected conditions for bubbling regime (◆◆◇◇) or turbulent regime (■■□□). Closed symbols: gas velocity constant. Open symbols: cross section constant.

Cabello, A., Abad, A., De las Obras Loscertales, M., Bartocci, P., García-Labiano, F., & de Diego, L. F. (2023). Exploring design options for pressurized chemical looping combustion of natural gas. *Fuel*, 342, 126983.

➤ Solids inventory and pressure drop

➤ Solids inventory and pressure drop

If pressure has a positive effect on reactivity, small differences in pressure drop would be expected

➤ Solids circulation rate (G_s) and oxygen transport capacity (R_{oc})

Dependent (mainly) on the gas flow in the air reactor

➤ Solids circulation rate (G_s) and oxygen transport capacity (R_{oc})

Dependent (mainly) on the gas flow in the air reactor

1 atm

Similar fluid dynamic conditions to those here assumed

➤ Solids circulation rate (G_s) and oxygen transport capacity (R_{oc})

Dependent (mainly) on the gas flow in the air reactor

1 atm

Similar fluid dynamic conditions to those here assumed

CFD MODELING

ASPEN MODELING

FUEL_REACTOR.apwz - Aspen Plus V11 - aspenONE

File Home Economics Batch Dynamics Plant Data Equation Oriented View Customize Resources

Cut METSOLID Unit Sets Next Run Step Stop Reset Control Panel Model Summary Input Stream Analysis Heat Exchanger Pressure Relief
 Copy Paste Clipboard Units Reconcile Stream Summary History Sensitivity Azeotrope Search PRD Rating Datasheets
 Settings Utility Costs Report Data Fit Distillation Synthesis Analysis Flare System Safety Analysis

Simulation

FR (Fluidbed) - Results x EO Configuration x Results Summary - Run Status x Main Flowsheet x Streams x S16 (MATERIAL) x R-1 (POWERLAW) - Input x

Stoichiometry Kinetic Equilibrium Activity Comments

New Edit Copy Paste

Rxn No.	Reaction type	Stoichiometry	Delete
1	Kinetic	NIO(MIXED) + H2 --> H2O(MIXED)	X

Edit Reaction

Reaction No. 1 Reaction type Kinetic

Component	Coefficient	Exponent
NIO (MIXED)	-1	1
H2	-1	

Component	Coefficient	Exponent
H2O		1

Next Close

Model Palette

Mixers/Splitters Separators Exchangers Columns Reactors Pressure Changers Manipulators Solids Solids Separators User Models Batch Models

MATERIAL Mixer FSplit SSplit

Required Input Incomplete Check Status

100% 01:29 28/03/2023

File Home Economics Batch Dynamics Plant Data Equation Oriented View Customize Resources

Search Exchange

Cut Copy Paste Clipboard METSOLID Unit Sets Next Run Step Stop Reset Control Panel Reconcile Settings Model Summary Stream Summary Utility Costs Input History Report Stream Analysis Sensitivity Data Fit Heat Exchanger Azeotrope Search Distillation Synthesis Pressure Relief PRD Rating Flare System Datasheets

Simulation Main Flowsheet S1 (MATERIAL) AIRREACT (Fluidbed) - Input Control Panel S3 (MATERIAL) Results Summary - Run Status R-1 (POWERLAW) - Input

All Items Setup Property Sets Analysis Flowsheet Streams S1 S2 S3 S4 S6 Blocks AIRREACT Input Block Options Results Stream Results Summary COMP Utilities Reactions R-1 Input Results EO Variables Convergence Flowsheeting Options Model Analysis Tools EO Configuration Results Summary Run Status Streams Convergence Operating Costs CO2 Emissions Properties Simulation Safety Analysis Energy Analysis

Stoichiometry Kinetic Equilibrium Activity Comments

1) H₂ + NIO(CIPSD) --> H₂O(MIXED)

Reacting phase: Liquid Rate basis: Reac (vol)

Power Law kinetic expression

If To is specified Kinetic factor = $k(T/T_o)^n e^{-(E/R)[1/T-1/T_o]}$

If To is not specified Kinetic factor = $kT^n e^{-E/RT}$

k: 0.0093
 n: 0.5
 E: 26 kJ/mol
 To: C
 [C] basis: Molarity

Edit Reactions Solids

Model Palette: Mixers/Splitters Separators Exchangers Columns Reactors Pressure Changers Manipulators Solids Solids Separators User Models Batch Models

MATERIAL Mixer FSplit SSplit

Input Changed Check Status

100% 02:25 28/03/2023

Nova LT16 GT

Thermoflow, Inc.

WHAT IS THERMOFLEX?

THERMOFLEX

Version 13.0.1
Copyright © 1995-2008
Thermoflow, Inc.

Warning: This computer program is protected by United States copyright law and international treaty provisions. Any unauthorized reproduction or distribution may result in severe civil and criminal penalties.

- THERMOFLEX is a fully-flexible program for heat balance modeling & engineering. Models are built graphically assembling components "lego-style".
- THERMOFLEX is used to model **Combined Cycles, Conventional Steam Plants, Process Plants, and more.**
- Performs both design and off-design calculations.
- Contains powerful "Logical Components" to model off-design controls.
- In combination with PEACE (Plant Engineering and Construction Estimator), it provides engineering details and cost estimation.
- THERMOFLEX works alone, or in concert with GT PRO, GT MASTER, and/or STEAM MASTER.

Prof. Silvia
Ravelli

NON REGENERATED

REGENERATED

Air reactor results

Air reactor results

GRACE DIAGRAM

Fuel Reactor results (1)

Fuel Reactor results (2)

GUIDELINES (1)

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

LEGEND

Article

Dimensioning Air Reactor and Fuel Reactor of a Pressurized Chemical Looping Combustor to Be Coupled to a Gas Turbine: Part 1, the Air Reactor

Pietro Bartocci ^{1,*}, Alberto Abad ¹, Aldo Bischi ², Lu Wang ³, Arturo Cabello ¹, Margarita de Las Obras Loscertales ¹, Mauro Zampilli ⁴, Haiping Yang ⁴ and Francesco Fantozzi ⁴

¹ Instituto de Carboquímica (C.S.I.C.), C. Miguel Luessma Castán 4, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain
² Department of Energy, Systems, Territory and Construction Engineering, University of Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56122 Pisa, Italy
³ State Key Laboratory of Coal Combustion, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Wuhan 430074, China
⁴ Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Perugia, Via G. Duranti 67, 06125 Perugia, Italy
 * Correspondence: pbartocci@sb.csic.es

Abstract: This paper provides a simple methodology for the design of the air reactor of a chemical looping combustor to optimize its characteristics when it is employed connected to a turbo expander to produce power. The design process, given a certain objective (e.g., electric power) defines the reactor specifics, namely height and diameter, taking into account the following aspects: solids inventory of the air reactor; gas velocity; air reactor transport disengaging height (TDH); solids concentration profile along the reactor height; dense bed height; freeboard height; pressure drop depending on air reactor injectors design and configuration. The total air reactor height was about 9.5 m, while the diameter was about 1.8 m. The total inventory was about 10,880 kg, while the circulation rate in the air reactor was about 110 kg/s. The operating pressure and temperature were, respectively, 12 bar and 1200 °C. The average velocity of the gases inside the reactor was about 4 m/s. The fluidization regime resulted to be comprised between turbulent and fast fluidization. Further work must be directed into the estimate of the pressure drop of the reactor, which will affect the plant efficiency in a considerable way.

Keywords: carbon negative technologies; gas turbines; pressurized chemical looping combustor; biofuels; Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage

1. Introduction

In both the Fifth Assessment and the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways reports, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) identifies Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) as a key set of technologies to meet the goal of limiting the increase in the global temperature to less than 2 °C, see [1]. BECCS is still under development; nevertheless, Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC) is considered to be a promising technology to implement it effectively—see for the recent work of [2]. Several aspects of chemical looping, see for example [3–6], have already been addressed, and there is a rising interest in Pressurized CLC (PCLC), as recently reported in [7]. This allows the capability to use both gaseous and solid fuels and simultaneously reach conversion efficiencies comparable to the state of the art of electric energy conversion represented by Natural Gas Combined Cycles (NGCC) via internal combustion such as in the gas turbines case, while having intrinsic separation of CO₂. Nevertheless, work on coupling of PCLC reactors with turbo expanders is still not complete, given that there are many challenges to address and considering the relative novelty of CLC technology.

In this context, a Marie Curie project has been funded by the European Commission and managed in the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Instituto de Carboquímica

Citation: Bartocci, P.; Abad, A.; Bischi, A.; Wang, L.; Cabello, A.; de Las Obras Loscertales, M.; Zampilli, M.; Yang, H.; Fantozzi, F. Dimensioning Air Reactor and Fuel Reactor of a Pressurized Chemical Looping Combustor to Be Coupled to a Gas Turbine: Part 1, the Air Reactor. *Energies* **2023**, *16*, 2102. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16052102>

Academic Editor: Antonio Galvagno
 Received: 4 July 2022
 Revised: 26 October 2022
 Accepted: 4 November 2022
 Published: 21 February 2023

Copyright: © 2023 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

GUIDELINES (2)

Article

Dimensioning Air Reactor and Fuel Reactor of a Pressurized CLC Plant to Be Coupled to a Gas Turbine: Part 2, the Fuel Reactor

Wang Lu ¹, Pietro Bartocci ^{2*}, Alberto Abad ², Aldo Bischi ³, Haiping Yang ¹, Arturo Cabello ², Margarita de Las Obras Loscertales ², Mauro Zampilli ⁴ and Francesco Fantozzi ⁴

¹ State Key Laboratory of Coal Combustion, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Wuhan 430074, China; luwang721@hust.edu.cn (W.L.); yhp2002@163.com (H.Y.)

² Instituto de Carboquímica (C.S.I.C.), C. Miguel Luesma Castán 4, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain; abad@icb.csic.es (A.A.); acabello@icb.csic.es (A.C.); mabras@icb.csic.es (M.d.L.O.L.)

³ Department of Energy, Systems, Territory and Construction Engineering, University of Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56122 Pisa, Italy; aldo.bischi@unipi.it

⁴ Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Perugia, Via G. Duranti 67, 06125 Perugia, Italy; mauro.zampilli@unipg.it (M.Z.); francesco.fantozzi@unipg.it (F.F.)

* Correspondence: pbartocci@icb.csic.es

Abstract: Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) technologies are fundamental to reach negative CO₂ emissions by removing it from the atmosphere and storing it underground. A promising solution to implement BECCS is pressurized Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC), which involves coupling a pressurized CLC reactor system to a turboexpander. The typical configuration chosen is to have an air reactor and a fuel reactor based on coupled circulating fluidized beds. The fluidization regime in both reactors is preferred to be fast fluidization to enhance gas particle contact and solids circulation among reactors. To design the two reactors, Aspen Plus software was used, given that the new version has a module for fluidized bed modeling. At first, the oxygen carrier was designed ex novo, but given that it is a composite compound mainly made by nickel oxide freeze-granulated on alumina (Ni40Al-FG), the molecular structure has been inserted in Aspen Plus. Then, based on the power of the gas turbine, the power output per kg of evolving fluid (in this case, depleted air) is calculated using Aspen Plus. Once the nitrogen content in the depleted air is known, the total air at the inlet of the air reactor is calculated. The fuel reactor is modeled by inserting the reduction reactions for nickel-based oxygen carriers. The paper presents a useful methodology for developing pressurized Chemical Looping Combustors to be coupled to gas turbines for power generation. The provided data will be cross-validated with 0D-models and experimental results.

Keywords: carbon negative technologies; gas turbines; pressurized chemical looping combustor; biofuels; BECCS

Citation: Lu, W.; Bartocci, P.; Abad, A.; Bischi, A.; Yang, H.; Cabello, A.; de Las Obras Loscertales, M.; Zampilli, M.; Fantozzi, F. Dimensioning Air Reactor and Fuel Reactor of a Pressurized CLC Plant to Be Coupled to a Gas Turbine: Part 2, the Fuel Reactor. *Energies* **2023**, *16*, 3850. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16093850>

Academic Editors: Roberta De Robbio and Maria Cristina Cameretti

Received: 3 August 2022

Revised: 7 November 2022

Accepted: 18 April 2023

Published: 30 April 2023

Copyright: © 2023 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

According to Kang et al. [1], more than 120 nations have made carbon neutrality pledges at current times [2,3]. In this context, Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) is considered an irreplaceable technology to achieve this target [4]. Together with CCS, the development of Negative Emissions Technologies (NET) is also advocated [5]. These are key technologies that are able to absorb CO₂ directly from the atmosphere and store it underground, while CCS is used “only” to prevent CO₂ from reaching the atmosphere and increasing the carbon dioxide concentration. Examples of NET are afforestation and reforestation, the increase of carbon content in soils, storing carbon in the soils in the form of biochar, Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (for BECCS see also [6]), Direct Air Carbon Capture and Storage (DACCS), and enhanced weathering and ocean fertilization [7]. However, what is the Technology Readiness Level of the many NET? In an

GUIDELINES (3)

1)

$$Q_{FR} = [(H_{CO_2}^0 * m_{CO_2} + m_{CO_2} * cp_{CO_2} * (T_{FR} - T_0)) + (H_{H_2O}^0 * m_{H_2O} + m_{H_2O} * H_{H_2O}) + (H_{Me}^0 * m_{Me} + m_{Me} * cp_{Me} * (T_{FR} - T_0))] - [(H_{MeO}^0 * m_{MeO} + m_{MeO} * cp_{MeO} * (T_{FR} - T_{AR})) + (H_{CH_4}^0 * m_{CH_4} + m_{CH_4} * cp_{CH_4} * (T_{FR} - T_{comp}))] + VR * \Delta P$$

2)

$$Q_{AR} = [H_{MeO}^0 * m_{MeO} + m_{MeO} * cp_{MeO} * (T_{AR} - T_0)] - [(H_{Me}^0 * m_{Me} + m_{Me} * cp_{Me} * (T_{AR} - T_{FR})) + ((m_{O_2st} * (alfa) * cp_{O_2} * (T_{AR} - T_{comp})) + (m_{N_2st} * alfa * cp_{N_2} * (T_{AR} - T_{comp})))] + VR * \Delta P$$

Conclusions

- The Marie Curie project GTCLC-NEG has proved that a microgt can be coupled to a pressurised CLC combustor effectively, the idea is feasible;
- This technology once electrolyser become very diffused could fight with cheap oxygen used for oxyfuel combustion
- But.... Oxygen can be made also with CLAS – see Cambridge university research and Brin process.

EXPLOITATION PLAN: DESIGN OF A LABORATORY CLAS AND CLC COMBUSTION

Item	Cost (£)
3D printed packed bed reactor	10,000
PC	1,000
3D printed microgt	15,000
Injectors	10,000
Gas analysis	50,000
Gas control, flowmeters, piping and valves	10,000
Bench DAQ and automation	20,000
Total	116,000

DESIGNING AND TESTING OF TURBO EXPANDER, Master Student Project at University of Sussex

Acknowledgments 1

Acknowledgments 2

Further information about the project

- <https://zenodo.org/communities/gtclc-neg/edit/>
- <https://pietrobartocci.wixsite.com/gtclc-neg>
- <https://twitter.com/gtclcneg2021>
- https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC2bKUmm7iXO03yYGsUf_oIQ
- <https://www.linkedin.com/in/pietro-bartocci-9a2b2626/>

GTCLC-NEG publications:

1. Cabello, A., Abad, A., De las Obras Loscertales, M., Bartocci, P., García-Labiano, F., & de Diego, L. F. (2023). Exploring design options for pressurized chemical looping combustion of natural gas. *Fuel*, 342, 126983.
2. Lu, W., Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Bischi, A., Yang, H., Cabello, A., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2023). Dimensioning Air Reactor and Fuel Reactor of a Pressurized CLC Plant to Be Coupled to a Gas Turbine: Part 2, the Fuel Reactor. *Energies*, 16(9), 3850.
3. Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Bischi, A., Wang, L., Cabello, A., de Las Obras Loscertales, M., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2023). Dimensioning Air Reactor and Fuel Reactor of a Pressurized Chemical Looping Combustor to Be Coupled to a Gas Turbine: Part 1, the Air Reactor. *Energies*, 16(5), 2102.
4. Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Flores, A. C., & de las Obras Loscertales, M. (2023). Ilmenite: A promising oxygen carrier for the scale-up of chemical looping. *Fuel*, 337, 126644.
5. Lu, W., Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Cabello, A., Loscertales, M. D. L. O., Mendiara, T., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2023). Evaluation of the effect of pressure and heat transfer on the efficiency of a batch fuel reactor, using Iron-based Oxygen Carrier with a CFD model. *Fuel*, 333, 126266.
6. Bartocci, P., Bidini, G., Abad, A., Bischi, A., Cabello, A., Loscertales, M. D. L. O., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2022, December). Pressurised Chemical Looping Combustion (PCLC): Air Reactor design. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2385, No. 1, p. 012127). IOP Publishing.
7. Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Mattisson, T., Cabello, A., de las Obras Loscertales, M., Negro, T. M., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2022). Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) developed by coupling a Pressurised Chemical Looping combustor with a turbo expander: How to optimize plant efficiency. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 169, 112851.
8. Serra, A., Gandini, S., Colantoni, S., Buia, G., Fantaccione, L., Bartocci, P., & Fantozzi, F. (2022, June). Additive Manufacturing Versus Investment Casting for a Gas Turbine Component: a Social Life Cycle Comparison. In *Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air* (Vol. 85987, p. V002T03A001). American Society of Mechanical Engineers.
9. Fantaccione, L., Serra, A., Buia, G., Bartocci, P., Gandini, S., & Fantozzi, F. (2022, June). Effects on Sustainability by Redesign of a 1° Stage Gas Turbine Nozzle Ring From Investment Casting to Additive Manufacturing: A Life Cycle Environmental Impact Comparison. In *Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air* (Vol. 85987, p. V002T03A002). American Society of Mechanical Engineers.
10. Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Cabello, A., de las Obras Loscertales, M., Lu, W., Yang, H., & Fantozzi, F. (2022). CFD Modelling of the Fuel Reactor of a Chemical Looping Combustion Plant to Be Used with Biomethane. *Processes*, 10(3), 588.
11. Bartocci, P., Abad Secades, A., Obras-Loscertales, M. D. L., Cabello Flores, A., Taiana, A., Joronen, T., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2021). Batch fluidized bed model in MFIX software for simulation of chemical looping combustion.
12. Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Cabello, A., Zampilli, M., Buia, G., Serra, A., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2021). Technical economic and environmental analysis of chemical looping versus oxyfuel combustion for NGCC power plant. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 312, p. 08019). EDP Sciences.

Further developments

0D REACTOR MODEL IN FORTRAN

```

-----main program
use devObject
implicit none
----- Executable
call open_devObjects
...
call userSub
...
call close_devObjects
end
-----end of main

subroutine userSub
use devObject
implicit none

integer, parameter :: size=1024
type (devVar) dv1, dv2, dv3, dv4

real ar1d1(size), ar1d2(size), ar1d3(size), ar1result(size)

call random_number(ar1d1)
call random_number(ar1d2)
call random_number(ar1d3)

dv1=allocate(dv1('real',size))
dv2=allocate(dv2('real',size))
dv3=allocate(dv3('real',size))

call transfer_f4(ar1d1,dv1,.true.)
call transfer_f4(ar1d2,dv2,.true.)
call transfer_f4(ar1d3,dv3,.true.)

!pointwise multiplication division addition subtraction test
dv4=(3.14159*dv1*(dv2+dv3)*dv1-(-.551+dv3)*dv2+(-.244)/dv1)

call transfer_f4(ar1result,dv4,.false.)

call deallocate(dv1)
call deallocate(dv2)
call deallocate(dv3)
call deallocate(dv4)
end subroutine userSub
    
```


NMPC Nonlinear model predictive controllers

PRESSURE CONTROL

Thanks for the attention!

GT GO

NEG O₂

Thanks for the attention!

—
NEG **GT** **2**

pbartocci78@gmail.com